

Copper(II) complexes with *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-iminodiacetic acid and benzohydrazide ligands : Synthesis, electrochemical, spectroscopic, antimicrobial and SOD activity

S. P. Rawat^a and Mukesh Choudhary^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, A. P. S. University, Rewa-486 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Patna-800 005, Bihar, India

E-mail : mukesh@nitp.ac.in

Manuscript received online 13 September 2013, revised 10 October 2013, accepted 12 October 2013

Abstract : Five new copper(II) complexes, viz. [Cu(HIda)(L¹)] 1; [Cu(HIda)(L²)] 2; [Cu(HIda)(L³)] 3; [Cu(HIda)(L⁴)] 4; [Cu(HIda)(L⁵)] 5; where HIda = *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-iminodiacetic acid; L¹ = benzoylhydrazide; L² = *N*-[(1-1-(2-methylphenyl)ethylidene)benzohydrazide]; L³ = *N*-[(1-1-(4-methylphenyl)ethylidene)benzohydrazide]; L⁴ = *N*-[(1-1-(2-methoxyphenyl)ethylidene)benzohydrazide]; L⁵ = *N*-[(1-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)ethylidene)benzohydrazide]; have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses, FAB (fast atomic bombardment), magnetic measurements, electronic absorption, conductivity measurements, cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy. The EPR spectra of these complexes in frozen solutions of DMSO showed a single at *g ca.* 2. The trend in *g*-value (*g*_{||} > *g*_⊥ > 2.00) suggest that the unpaired electron on copper(II) has *d*_{x²-y²} character. The superoxide dismutase activity reveals that these complexes catalyze the fast disproportionation of superoxide in DMSO solution. The antibacterial and antifungal activities of the complexes have also been investigated.

Keywords : Copper(II) complexes, EPR, CV, SOD activity, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

The synthesis of low-molecular weight copper(II) complexes mimicking the superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity¹⁻³, provide models for metalloproteinase active sites and lend insight toward the design of new catalysts. Among these complexes, copper(II) complexes are known to play a significant role in naturally occurring biological systems⁴, like (Cu, Zn-SOD) superoxide dismutase. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) which can destroy the superoxide very rapidly, is nature's agent for protection of these organism from this radical burden. In fact native SOD enzymes have been shown in many studies to exhibit protection in animal models of inflammatory diseases⁵. Oberley and Buettner⁶ have reported that cancer cells had less superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity than normal cells. Superoxide ion is toxic to cells; a defense mechanism must have been initiated by nature. All organisms, which use dioxygen and many that have to survive an oxygenated environment, contain at least one SOD. The SOD shows bio catalytic activity towards the dismutation

of superoxide according to the following mechanism.

This has led to successful testing of Cu^{II}₂(aspirinate)₄ and copper(II) salicylates against the growth of solid tumors in implanted mice. Subsequently, several octahedral copper(II) complexes [Cu^{II}₂(aspirinate)₂L₂], where L₂ is pyridine, dimethyl sulphoxide, 4-picoline, imidazole, 1-methylimidazole, have been synthesized and SOD activity of these octahedral complexes measured⁷. Copper complexes have shown anti-inflammatory, antitumor, anticonvulsant, anti-diabetic, anticancer, anti-carcinogenic, anti-mutagenic and radio protectant activities in animal models of diseased states^{8,9}. In the past decade benzoylhydrazones are extensively used in research. They have emerged as an important class of nitrogen-oxygen donor ligands particularly for transition metal ions. The real impetus towards developing in coordination chemistry of these hydrazones have been provided by remark-

able biological activities observed for these compounds which has been shown to be related to their metal complex activity. Johnson *et al.*¹⁰, have found that benzoylhydrazone and their derivative have strong insecticidal activity against various insects. In a previous paper^{11,12} we reported mixed-ligand octahedral metal(II) complexes with tris(2-aminoethylamine) and N, N donor ligands. In continuation of our work¹³ on copper(II) complexes, we here describes the synthesis, electrochemical, spectroscopic, antimicrobial and SOD activity of octahedral copper(II) complexes namely [Cu(HIida)(L¹)] **1**; [Cu(HIida)(L²)] **2**; [Cu(HIida)(L³)] **3**; [Cu(HIida)(L⁴)] **4**; [Cu(HIida)(L⁵)] **5**. Scheme 1 represents all the ligands

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Schiff base ligands (L¹-L⁵) in a generalized form.

(L¹-L⁵) in a generalized form possessing N and O donor atom. HIida is a dibasic tetradentate ligand which having O₃N donor sites (Scheme 2). The SOD activities have been measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical (O₂⁻) and nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT) as O₂⁻ scavenger.

Scheme 2. Tentative structure of *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-iminodiacetic acid (HIida).

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Copper(II) chloride dihydrate was purchased from S.D. fine chemicals, India. All other chemicals used were of synthetic grade and used without further purification. Elemental analysis (C, H, N) of new octahedral copper(II) complexes were performed on Elementor Vario ELIII Carlo Erba 1108 analyser. FAB (*m/z*) mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol s-102/DA 6000 mass spectrometer using (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature (RT) with *m*-nitro benzoyl alcohol as the matrix. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance using a mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) as calibrating agent ($x_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units). The molar susceptibilities were corrected for the diamagnetism of the constituent atoms by using Pascal constants. UV-Vis spectra were recorded at 25 °C on a Shimadzu UV-Vis recording spectrophotometer UV-1601 in quartz cells. IR spectra were recorded in KBr medium on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer X-band (~9.4 GHz). The EPR parameters for copper(II) complexes were determined accurately using simulation program¹⁴. EPR spectra were recorded with a Varian E-line Century Series Spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band with 100 kHz modulation frequency at room temperature and at 77 K. TCNE was used as field marker. The frozen solution at 77 K used for EPR spectra were in 3×10^{-3} M of DMSO solution. The EPR parameters for copper(II) complexes were determined accurately using simulation program. Cyclic voltammetry was carried out

with a BAS-100 Epsilon electrochemical analyzer having an electrochemical cell with a three-electrode system. Ag/AgCl was used as a reference electrode, glassy carbon as working electrode and platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode. NaClO₄ (0.1 M) was used as supporting electrolyte and DMSO as solvent. All measurements were carried out at 298 K under a nitrogen atmosphere.

Superoxide dismutase activity :

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activities were evaluated using the following methods. The *in vitro* SOD activity was measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical (O₂⁻) and nitrobluetetrazolium chloride (NBT) as O₂⁻ scavenger¹⁵. In general, 400 µL sample to be assayed was added to a solution containing 2.1 mL of 0.2 mol L⁻¹ potassium phosphate buffer (pH 8.6) and 1 mL of 56 µmol L⁻¹ alkaline DMSO solution prepared under similar condition in DMSO (except NaOH). A unit of SOD activity is the concentration of complex, which causes 50% inhibition of alkaline DMSO-mediated reduction of NBT.

Antibacterial activity :

The *in vitro* antimicrobial (antibacterial) activities of these complexes were tested against Gram (+) *Streptococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* using paper disc diffusion method^{16,17}. The liquid medium containing the bacterial subcultures was autoclaved for 20 min at 121 °C and at 15 lb pressure before inoculation. The bacteria were then cultured for 24 h at 36 °C in an incubator. Nutrient agar was poured into a plate and allowed to solidify. The test compound (DMSO) were added drop wise to a 10 mm diameter filter paper disc placed at a center of each agar plate. The plates were then kept at 5 °C for 1 h the transferred to a incubator maintained at 36 °C. The width of the growth inhibition zone around the disc was measured after 24 h incubation. Four replicates were made for each treatment.

Antifungal activity :

The antifungal activity of the compounds has been evaluated against *Aspergillus* sp. and *Penicillium* sp. by the Radial Growth method^{18,19} using Czapek's agar medium. The compounds were directly with the medium in 5, 10 and 15 mM concentrations. Controls were also run and four replicated were used in each case. The linear growth of the fungus was obtained by measuring the diameter of the fungal colony after four days. The amount of growth inhibition in all the replicates was calculated

by the equation, Percent inhibition = $C - T/C \times 100$, where, *C* is the fungal colony in the control plate and *T* is the diameter of the fungal colony in the test plate.

Synthesis of L², L³, L⁴ and L⁵ :

The Schiff bases L², L³, L⁴ and L⁵ were prepared by general condensation reaction. A methanol solution of benzoylhydrazide (10 mmol, 1.36 g) was stirred with (10 mL) of 2-methyl acetophenone (10 mmol, 1.34 g), 4-methyl acetophenone (10 mmol, 1.34 g), 2-methoxy acetophenone (10 mmol, 1.50 g), 4-methoxy acetophenone (10 mmol, 1.50 g) respectively. The precipitate was obtained, washed with cold methanol and diethyl ether, dried in air and stored in a CaCl₂ desiccator. Yield varied at the range 80–90%. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₆N₂O (L²) : Found : (%) C, 76.09; H, 6.74; N, 11.09. Calcd. (%) C, 76.07; H, 6.32; N, 11.07; FAB-mass (*m/z*); Calcd. 252.33, Found 252. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₆N₂O (L³) : Calcd. (%) C, 76.07; H, 6.32; N, 11.07. Found (%) : C, 76.09; H, 6.34; N, 11.09; FAB-mass (*m/z*) Calcd. 252.33, Found 252. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₆N₂O₂ (L⁴) : Anal. Calcd. C, 71.50; H, 5.91, N, 10.40. Found (%) : C, 71.48; H, 5.40; N, 10.38; FAB-mass (*m/z*) 268.33. Found : 268. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₆N₂O₂ (L⁵) : Anal. Calcd. (%) C, 71.55; H, 5.96; N, 10.43. Found : (%) C, 71.50; H, 5.91; N, 10.40; FAB-mass (*m/z*) Calcd. 268.33, Found : 268.

Synthesis of [Cu(HIida)(L¹)] (1) :

To a methanol solution (20 ml) of copper(II) chloride dihydrate (1.0 mmol, 0.170 g) a solution of HIida (1.0 mmol, 0.210 g) in methanol was added with constant stirring at RT. After the completion of the reaction, bh (1.0 mmol, 0.136 g) was added at constant stirring. The blue precipitate was collected by filtration and washed with MeOH. The solid was dried in air at room temperature and stored in a CaCl₂ dessicator. Yield 0.4 g (85%). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₅CuN₃O₄ **1** : C, 43.25; H, 4.15; N, 11.64%. Found : C, 43.20; H, 4.10; N, 11.59%; FAB-mass (*m/z*) Calcd. 360.69, Found : 360.

Synthesis of [Cu(HIida)(L²)] (2); [Cu(HIida)(L³)] (3); [Cu(HIida)(L⁴)] (4); [Cu(HIida)(L⁵)] (5) :

All these complexes were prepared by simple fashion as complex **1** by using metal salt and corresponding ligands. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₃CuN₃O₄ **2** : C, 52.84; H, 4.82; N, 8.80%. Found : C, 52.79; H, 4.77; N, 8.75%; FAB-mass (*m/z*) Calcd. 476.87, Found : 476. Anal. Calcd.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of copper(II) complexes 1-5.

for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{CuN}_3\text{O}_4$ **3** : C, 52.84; H, 4.82; N, 8.80%. Found: C, 52.79; H, 4.77; N, 8.75%; FAB-mass (m/z) Calcd. 476.87, Found : 476. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{CuN}_3\text{O}_7$ **4** : C, 51.12; H, 4.66; N, 8.52%. Found : C, 51.10; H, 4.61; N, 8.47%; FAB-mass (m/z) Calcd. 492.87, Found : 492. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{CuN}_3\text{O}_7$ **5** : C, 51.12; H, 4.66; N, 8.52%. Found : C, 51.10; H, 4.61; N, 8.47%; FAB-mass (m/z) Calcd. 492.87, Found : 492.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

The mononuclear complexes prepared in high yield by reacting copper(II) salt with N -(2-hydroxyethyl)-2-iminodiacetic acid and L^1 - L^5 in 1 : 1 molar ratio to give complexes of general composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{B})]$. The reactions proceed in the following manner (Scheme 3).

where, A = HIda, B = L¹-L⁵. The Schiff base ligands was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of benzoylhydrazine and 2-methyl acetophenone, 4-methyl acetophenone, 2-methoxy acetophenone, 4-methoxy acetophenone respectively, in ethanol for 3 h. Complexes are blue (1), light blue (2 and 3), yellow (4), red (5) are stable in air, partially soluble in water but soluble in most of organic solvent. There were characterized by microanalysis, FAB⁺ spectrometry and then by electrochemical and spectroscopic techniques. All the complexes decompose between 200 and 350 °C. Very low values of molar conductance (2.51–7.32 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) of 10⁻³ M solution of the complexes in DMSO at room temperature indicate that they are non-electrolytes²⁰. The present copper(II) complexes are paramagnetic in solid state at room temperature as expected from *d*⁹ electronic configuration of Cu^{II} ion. The observed magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) of the copper(II) complexes are 1.77, 1.78, 1.80, 1.82 and 1.86 B.M. respectively. Be more specific about the other reported octahedral copper(II) complexes²¹⁻²³, and are consistent with spin only magnetic moment of 1.732 B.M. for a *S* = ½.

EPR investigation :

The EPR spectral of the complexes in the polycrystalline state at 298 K and in solution at 77 K were recorded, in the X-band region, using 100 KHz field modulation and the *g*-factors were quoted relatively to the standard marker TCNE (*g* = 2.00277). The EPR spectral assignments of the copper(II) complexes along with the spin Hamiltonian and orbital reduction parameters are given in Table 1. Some representative figures are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. As powder at room temperature [Cu(HIda)(L¹)] 1 gives two anisotropic signals with *g*_{||} at 2.1990 and *g*_⊥ at 2.0580, suggesting an axial symmetry with all principal axes aligned parallel, the geometry is proposed to be an elongated tetragonally-distorted octahedron. *G* = 4.0533 suggest that the local tetragonal axes are only slightly misaligned. Powder spectra of [Cu(HIda)(L²)] 2; show a rhombic signal with *g*_{||} and *g*_⊥ typical for (lowest *g* > 2.04) copper(II) ion in an elongated rhombic symmetry with all the axes aligned parallel, consistent with distorted octahedral stereochemistry¹⁶. The large rhombicity of the *g*-tensor can be explained as

Table 1. EPR spectral parameters of the copper(II) complexes

Parameters	1	2	3	4	5
Polycrystalline state (298 K)					
<i>g</i>	2.1990	2.2035	2.1990	2.2140	2.2100
<i>g</i> _⊥	2.0580	2.0550	2.5020	2.0590	2.0550
<i>g</i> _{iso} or <i>g</i> _{av}	2.1050	2.1045	2.1010	2.1107	2.1325
DMSO (77 K)					
<i>g</i>	2.1990	2.210	2.268	2.233	2.240
<i>g</i> _⊥	2.0580	2.056	2.073	2.069	2.076
<i>A</i> (G)	200	196	195	195	200
<i>G</i>	3.6799	3.7033	3.5525	3.8080	3.7053
α ²	0.8156	0.7706	0.8235	0.8272	0.8272
β ²	0.9248	0.9148	0.9083	0.9199	0.9199
γ ²	0.8527	0.9388	0.8452	0.8667	0.8367
<i>K</i>	0.7298	0.7445	0.7360	0.7592	0.7503
<i>K</i> _⊥	0.7767	0.7621	0.7399	0.7858	0.7559

Fig. 1. EPR spectra of complexes 1 in DMSO (3 × 10⁻³ M) in powder at 298 K.

highly distorted coordination geometry around copper(II) and suggests that the ground state wave functions have considerable admixture of the excited state. This is further supported by the calculated *R* factor [*R* = (*g*₂ - *g*₁) / (*g*₃ - *g*₂)] which is less than unity (*R* = 0.41), suggesting an essentially *d*_{x²-y² ground state^{24,25}. The geometric parameter *G* which is measure of exchange of interaction between the copper centers in a polycrystalline solid has been calculated. According to Hathaway^{26,27} if *G* > 4, the exchange interaction is negligible and if *G* < 4, indi-}

Fig. 2. EPR spectra of complex **1** at 77 K.

cate exchange interaction. The value of G for present complexes is found to be range 3.55–3.80 indicating exchange interaction in solid state. The EPR parameter and $d-d$ transition energies were used to evaluate the bonding parameter α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 (Table 1) which may be regarded as measure of the covalence of the in-plane σ -bonding and in-plane π - and out-of-plane π bonding, respectively. The in-plane σ -bonding parameter, α^2 was calculated by using the expression²⁸. $\alpha^2 = (A_{||}/0.036) + (g_{||} - 2.0023) + 3/7 (g_{\perp} - 2.0023) + 0.04$. The orbital reduction factors $K_{||}$ and K_{\perp} were estimated from the expression²² $K_{||}^2 = (g_{||} - 2.0023) E_{d-d}/8\lambda_0$, $K_{\perp}^2 = (g_{\perp} - 2.0023) E_{d-d}/2\lambda_0$, where $K_{||} = \alpha^2 \beta^2$ and $K_{\perp} = \alpha^2 \gamma^2$ and λ_0 represents the one electron spin orbit coupling constant for the free ion, equal to -828 cm^{-1} . Significant information about the nature of bonding in the copper(II) complexes can be derived from the magnitude of $K_{||}$ and K_{\perp} . In case of pure σ -bonding $K_{||} \approx K_{\perp} \approx 0.77$ whereas $K_{||} < K_{\perp}$ implies considerable in-plane bonding, while for out-of-plane bonding $K_{||} > K_{\perp}$. In all the present copper(II) complexes, it is observed that $K_{||} < K_{\perp}$ which indicates the presence of significant in-plane bonding. The evaluated value of α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 of the complexes are consistent with both strong in-plane σ and in-plane π bonding.

Infrared spectral studies :

The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ bond of the ligand at 1652 cm^{-1} is found to be shifted to lower energies ($1598\text{--}1602 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the spectra of the complexes indicating the coordination via

the azomethine nitrogen. This is confirmed by the bands in the range $445\text{--}476 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which have been assigned to the $\nu(\text{Cu}\text{--}\text{N})$ band²⁹. These complexes **1-5** exhibit the $\nu_a(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ at $1635\text{--}1670$ and $1300\text{--}1380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively³⁰. Vibrations at $447\text{--}446 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (weak) (and expected below 400 cm^{-1} : out of our measuring limit) can be attributed to M-O and M-N vibrations^{31,32}.

UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy :

The electronic spectra of the complexes **1-3** were recorded in CH_2Cl_2 while the other two complexes were recorded in DMSO solution at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The bluish colors complex **1** exhibits a broad band at 592 nm (Fig. 4), similar to those reported for a copper(II) ion in octahedral environment^{33,34}. The $d-d$ transition for complexes **2-5** is observed as a broad band at $596\text{--}612 \text{ nm}$. Spectra of these complexes are dominated by the intense ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT) band at $418\text{--}421 \text{ nm}$ with a shoulder at $463\text{--}473 \text{ nm}$. Similar type of observations for $d-d$ band and MLCT band were reported for a copper(II) distorted octahedral geometry³⁵.

Cyclic voltammetry measurements :

The electrochemical properties of the these complexes have been studied by cyclic voltammetry (CV) under a nitrogen atmosphere in DMSO solution in the potential range $+1.00\text{--}9.00 \text{ V}$ versus Ag/AgCl reference and the results are presented in Table 2. A representative CV is

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Cu}(\text{HIda})(\text{L}^1)]$ **1** in 0.1 M NaClO_4 as supporting electrolyte [scan rate : 100 mV/s].

Fig. 4. The UV-Vis spectra ($3 \times 10^{-3} M$) of complex **1**.

shown in Fig. 3. The cyclic voltammograms of these complexes exhibit only one irreversible $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ redox couple^{36,37}. The difference in $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ redox potential among these complexes **1-5** demonstrates that the coordination environments around the copper(II) ions are different and afford a substantial explanation for the difference in SOD activity of them. It is known that an adequate $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ redox potential for effective catalysis of superoxide radical must be required between -0.405 V versus

SCE for $\text{O}_2/\text{O}_2^- + 0.645 \text{ V}$ versus SCE for $\text{O}_2^-/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$. Though it is inappropriate to compare the E° values with the reduction potentials of the two complexes in DMSO should be in the allowed range of an SOD mimic, since the obtained results of IC_{50} show that these have relatively low activity. Two reduction waves at high negative potential are assigned to the reduction of ligand. The pertinent redox couples are represented in the following electron transfer series (eq. (5)).

Superoxide dismutase activity :

SOD mimetic activities of the present complexes have also been measured. The SOD mimetic activities of the present complexes were examined by the NBT assay³⁸ following kinetically the reduction of NBT to MF^+ at 562 nm. Superoxide was enzymatically supplied from alkaline DMSO. The count fraction causing 50% inhibition of NBT reduction is called IC_{50} concentration, equivalent to one unit of SOD activity (IC_{50} values), together with the IC_{50} values of native SOD are given in Table 3 and Fig. 5. The IC_{50} values of these complexes ($50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **1**, $52 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **2**, $53 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **3**, $55 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **4**, $54 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **5**) are higher than

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetric measurements of copper(II) complexes

Scan rate (mV/s)	E_{pc} (mv)	I_{pc} (μA)	E_{pa} (mv)	I_{pa} (μA)	ΔE_{p}	E'_0	$I_{\text{pa}}/I_{\text{pc}}$ (μA)
[Cu(HIda)(L¹)] 1							
100	-514	2.0120	-290	0.9121	224	403	0.453
200	-528	2.6823	-278	1.1961	250	404	0.445
[Cu(HIda)(L²)] 2							
100	-554	2.8441	-379	1.1717	236	437	0.411
200	-608	12.9897	-264	5.4148	344	437	0.416
[Cu(HIda)(L³)] 3							
100	-858	2.8085	-538	1.5380	320	700	0.547
200	-870	4.2800	-528	2.3000	342	701	0.537
[Cu(HIda)(L⁴)] 4							
100	-674	1.5728	-380	0.7148	292	529	0.454
200	-686	2.2248	-368	1.0118	318	528	0.454
[Cu(HIda)(L⁵)] 5							
100	-510	1.6450	-184	0.8748	326	348	0.532
200	-584	2.9656	-110	1.5324	474	348	0.516

$$\Delta E_{\text{p}} = E_{\text{pa}} - E_{\text{pc}}; E'_0 = (E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}})/2$$

Table 3. Superoxide dismutase activity of some copper(II) complexes

Sr. No.	Complexes	IC ₅₀ ($\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$)	Ref.
1.	[Cu(glygly)].3H ₂ O	132	7
2.	[Cu(SAA)(Phen)]	50	44
3.	[Cu(SAA)(MeImH)]	35	43
4.	[Zn(Salgly)(Phen)H ₂ O]	6.15	43
5.	[Cu(Salgly)(Phen)H ₂ O]	0.79	43
6.	[Cu(BPS)(N ₃)]	29	43
7.	[Cu(BPS)(CNS)(H ₂ O)]NO ₃	11	43
8.	[Cu(Hhida)(BenzImH)].H ₂ O	43	45
9.	[Cu(Hhida)(EtImH)].H ₂ O	47	45
10.	[Cu(HIda)(L ¹)] 1	50	This work
11.	[Cu(HIda)(L ²)] 2	52	This work
12.	[Cu(HIda)(L ³)] 3	53	This work
13.	[Cu(HIda)(L ⁴)] 4	55	This work
14.	[Cu(HIda)(L ⁵)] 5	54	This work

Fig. 5. Superoxide dismutase activity of [Cu(HIda)(L¹)] **1**.

the value exhibited by the native enzyme ($\text{IC}_{50} = 0.04 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$) on a molar base (note that the smaller the IC_{50} value, the higher the SOD activity). The SOD activity of present complexes in the increasing order $1 < 2 < 3 < 5 < 4$. IC_{50} value order is similar to our previous work³⁹. The observed IC_{50} values of the present complexes are comparable with the various reported values for the copper(II) complexes^{40,41}, but are less active than the native SOD. The good activities of complexes may be attributed to the flexible HIda, bidentate ligands (L¹–L⁵) and copper ion which is able to accommodate the geo-

metrical change from Cu^{II} to Cu^I, which are proposed to be easily substituted by the substrate O₂⁻ in the catalytic process, just like the O₂⁻, in place of H₂O bound to copper site in the mechanism of dismutation of O₂⁻ by native SOD. Complex **1-5** show lower IC_{50} , and exhibits higher SOD activity than other mononuclear complexes except for two systems including native SOD so for reported⁴²⁻⁴⁷.

Antimicrobial activity :

All the synthesized compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against the Gram (+) bacteria *Streptococcus aureus* the Gram (-) bacteria *E. coli* and antifungal activity against *Penicillium* sp. and *Aspergillus* sp. which exhibited a markedly enhancement of activity on further coordination with the Cu^{II} ions against all the test bacteria/fungal strains. Four concentrations of the complexes were taken, i.e. 5 mM, 10 mM, 15mM and 20 mM. Certain strains of bacteria towards the present copper(II) complexes were determined by measuring the size of inhibition diameter. Complexes **1** and **2** have shown excellent antibacterial activity against *E. coli* comparable to that of *Streptococcus aureus*. They inhibited the bacterial growth up to 15–20% at 20 mM whereas others have poor antibacterial activity. The antibacterial and antifungal activity of complex **1** is graphically presented in Figs. 6 and 7. Both the bacteria are pathogens for humans, which causes dysentery and food poisoning, respectively. The area of zone of inhibition is less in the concentration of 5 mM in both micro-organisms and more in 20 mM concentration. This kind of observation is suggestive of that these complexes are effective against both pathogens. In case of complex **1** diameter of inhibition zone is highest for *E. coli* (Table 4) the antibacterial activity data show that Gram (+) bacteria *S. aureus* are more susceptible to test compounds than the Gram (-) bacteria *E. coli* which is in accordance with previous studies⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰. The weak antibacterial activity against Gram (-) bacteria was ascribed to the presence of an inter membrane⁵¹. It was observed that complex **2** is more active than **1**. Among fungal species two isolates were taken into consideration and were *Aspergillus* sp. and *Penicillium* sp. The zone of inhibition of these compounds against those fungi was recorded in Table 5. Similar trends were observed as in the case of bacteria. It was noted that *Penicillium* sp. was highly susceptible against complex **1**. Another fungi *As-*

Fig. 6. Antibacterial activity of [Cu(HIda)(L¹)] 1.

Fig. 7. Antifungal activity of [Cu(HIda)(L¹)] 1.

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of copper(II) complexes

Complexes (mM)	Diameter of inhibition zone (in mm)	
	<i>Streptococcus aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
[Cu(HIda)(L¹)] 1		
5	5	8
10	8	10
15	12	14
20	16	20
[Cu(HIda)(L²)] 2		
5	8	13
10	10	15
15	14	16
20	18	20
20	20	23

pergillus sp. showed least effectiveness against complex 2; but comparatively more susceptible towards 1 (Table 5). Such increased activity of the metal chelates can be explained the basis of overtones concept^{52,53} and Tweedy's chelation theory⁵⁴. These complexes also disturb the respiratory processes of the cell and thus block the synthesis of the protein, which restricts further growth of the organism.

Table 5. Antifungal activity of copper(II) complexes

Complexes (mM)	% Inhibition of spore germination	
	<i>Aspergillus</i> sp. (mg mL ⁻¹)	<i>Penicillium</i> sp. (mg mL ⁻¹)
[Cu(HIda)(L¹)] 1		
5	8	11
10	12	14
15	14	18
20	20	22
[Cu(HIda)(L²)] 2		
5	6	12
10	8	14
15	12	16
20	14	20
20	16	24

Conclusion

Five new copper(II) complexes, viz. [Cu(HIda)(L¹)] 1; [Cu(HIda)(L²)] 2; [Cu(HIda)(L³)] 3; [Cu(HIda)(L⁴)] 4; [Cu(HIda)(L⁵)] 5 have been synthesized and characterized by various physico-chemical and spectroscopic techniques. The magnetic and spectroscopic data of complexes

1-5 indicate octahedral geometry. The SOD activity of reported complexes in the increasing order $1 < 2 < 3 < 5 < 4$. Complexes 1 and 2 have shown excellent antibacterial activity against *E. coli* comparable to that of *Streptococcus aureus*. The antifungal activity of present complexes against *Aspergillus* sp. and *Penicillium* sp. indicate that the test compounds are more active against *Penicillium* sp. than the *Aspergillus* sp.

Acknowledgement

Our grateful thanks are due to the RSIC (SAIF), IIT Mumbai for EPR measurements. The Head, RSIC (SAIF), Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow is also thankfully acknowledged for providing analytical and spectral facilities. School of Environment Biology, A. P. S. University, Rewa (Madhya Pradesh), India for his help in antibacterial and antifungal screening. Financial assistance from UGC, Bhopal (F. No. MS-25/101030/07-08/CRO) and Rajiv Gandhi National Fellowship Scheme (UGC Scheme No. F.16-17/2006 (SA-III)), New Delhi, India are also thankfully acknowledged.

References

- U. Weser, L. M. Schubert and E. Lengfelder, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1963, **13**, 249.
- M. G. B. Drew, M. McCann and S. M. Nelson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 1868.
- C. A. Salata, M. T. Youinou and C. J. Burrows, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 3454.
- J. J. R. Frausto da Silva and R. J. P. Williams, in "The Biological Chemistry of the Elements", 2nd ed., Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2001, 1.
- J. M. McCord, *Biol. Med.*, 1986, **2**, 307.
- L. W. Oberley and G. R. Buettner, *Cancer Res*, 1979, **39**, 1141.
- R. G. Bhirud and T. S. Shrivastava, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1991, **179**, 125.
- J. R. G. Sorenson, *Chem. Ber.*, 1989, **21**, 169.
- J. R. G. Sorenson, V. Kishore, A. Pezeshk, L. W. Oberley and S. W. C. Leuthauser, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **91**, 285.
- K. Johnson, T. B. Murphy, N. J. Rose, W. H. Goodwin and L. Pickiest, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, **67**, 159.
- R. N. Patel, M. K. Kesharwani, A. Singh, D. K. Patel and M. Choudhary, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2008, **33**, 733.
- R. N. Patel, K. K. Shukla, A. Singh, M. Choudhary, D. K. Patel, J. Niclos-Gutierrez and D. Choquesillo-Lazarte, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2009, **34**, 239.
- R. N. Patel, S. P. Rawat, M. Choudhary, V. P. Sondhiya, D. K. Patel, K. K. Shukla, Y. Singh and R. Pandey, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2012, **392**, 283.
- G. Glugliarelli and S. Cannistraro, *Nuova Cimento*, 2004, **4D**, 231.
- R. G. Bhirud and T. S. Shrivastava, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **179**, 121.
- D. Liu and K. Kwasniewka, *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 1981, **27**, 289.
- H. B. Gray and J. Ballhausen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
- V. P. Singh, A. Katiyar and S. Singh, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 1336.
- I. Tabushi, Y. Taniguchi and H. Kato, *Tetrahedron*, 1977, **12**, 1049.
- W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
- A. Valent, M. Kotiutova, O. Svajlenova, D. Huclecova, P. Olejnikova and M. Melnik, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2004, **57**, 1279.
- R. N. Patel, N. Singh and V. L. N. Gundla, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 257.
- R. N. Patel, K. K. Shukla, A. Singh, M. Choudhary, U. K. Chauhan and S. Dwivedi, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 2009, **362**, 4891.
- O. I. Singh, M. Damayanti, N. R. Singh, R. K. H. Singh, M. Mohapatra and R. M. Kadam, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 909.
- I. S. Ahuja and S. Tripathi, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1991, **47**, 637.
- R. J. Rudely and B. J. Hathaway, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 1725.
- B. J. Hathaway and D. E. Billing, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 143.
- G. F. Bryce, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 3549.
- D. X. West, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1984, **43**, 3169.
- D. X. West and N. M. Kozub, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 52.
- K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and coordination compounds", 5th ed., Wiley, New York, 1997.
- M. Boca, M. Izakavic, G. Kickelbick, M. Valko, F. Renz, H. Fuess and K. Matuzsna, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 1913.
- R. N. Patel, N. Singh, K. K. Shukla, U. K. Chauhan, S. Chakraborty, J. Nicolas-Gutierrez and A. Castineiras, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **357**, 2469.
- R. N. Patel, N. Singh, K. K. Shukla, U. K. Chauhan, S. Chakraborty, J. Niclos-Gutierrez and A. Castineiras, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2004, **95**, 231.
- A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.

36. L. Sacconi and M. Ciampolini, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 276.
37. E. K. Efthimiadou, H. Thomadaki, Y. Sanakis, P. C. Raptopoulou, N. Katsaros, A. Scoria's, A. Karaliota and G. Psomas, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2007, **101**, 64.
38. V. T. Kasumov, F. Koksai and A. Seizer, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 1203.
39. R. N. Patel, M. Choudhary, K. K. Shukla, N. Singh and A. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 789.
40. J. L. Pierrs, P. Chautemps, S. Refit, C. Beguine, A. E. Marzouki, G. Serra Trice, E. Saint-Amman and P. Rey, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **117**, 965.
41. M. Devereux, D. O. Shea, A. Kellet, M. McCann, M. Walsh, D. Egan, C. Deegan, K. Kedziora, G. Rosair and H. Muller-Buns, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2006, **100**, 1389.
42. R. N. Patel, K. K. Shukla, A. Singh, D. K. Patel and V. P. Sondhiya, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2011, **64**, 902.
43. (a) R. N. Patel, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2010, **63**, 1207; (b) R. N. Patel, S. Kumar and K. B. Pandeya, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2002, **89**, 61.
44. R. N. Patel, V. L. N. Gundla and D. K. Patel, *Polyhedron*, 2008, **27**, 1054.
45. (a) R. N. Patel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2010, **363**, 3838; (b) R. N. Patel, A. Singh, K. K. Shukla, D. K. Patel and V. P. Sondhia, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 10.1007/s11243-010-9366-x (2010).
46. R. N. Patel, K. K. Shukla, A. Singh, M. Choudhary, D. K. Patel, J. Niclos-Gutierrez and D. Choquesillo-Lazarte, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2010, **63**, 3648.
47. J. Han, Y. Xing, C. Wang, P. Hou, F. Bai, X. Zeng, X. Zhang and M. Ge, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 745.
48. F. Simoncini, R. Rang one and C. Calanni, Farnance Ed., Part, **23(10)** 559 (1968), (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1968, **69**, 109851).
49. H. W. Seely and P. J. Van Demark, "Microbes in Action, Laboratory of Microbiology", 3rd ed., W. H. Freeman and Co., USA, 1981, 385.
50. R. N. Patel, N. Singh, K. K. Shukla, U. K. Chauhan, J. Niclos-Gutierrez and A. Castineiras, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **357**, 2476.
51. M. T. H. Tarafder, K. B. Chew, K. A. Crouse, A. M. Ali, B. M. Yamin and H. K. Fun, *Polyhedron*, 2002, **21**, 2683.
52. C. M. Mann, S. D. Cox and J. L. Markham, *Letters in Applied Microbiology*, 2006, **30**, 294.
53. Y. Anjaneyula and R. P. Rao, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1986, **16**, 257.
54. B. G. Tweedy, *Phytopathology*, 1964, **55**, 910.

